

DaedalusCAM: Testing the accuracy of hyperhemispheric cameras for the geological analysis on lunar analogues. J. E. Suarez-Valencia¹, M. Massironi¹, B. Casarotto¹, K. Toyokawa², R. Pozzobon¹, C. A. De Donno³, M. Mucci Beltrami³, C. Pernechele⁴, E. Simioni⁴, D. Scaccabarozzi⁵, and the DaedalusCAM Team. 1 University of Padova (javier.suarez@unipd.it), 2 University of Tokyo, 3 Planetek Italia S. r. l., 4 INAF-OAPD, 5 Politecnico di Milano.

Introduction: DaedalusCAM is an infrastructure intended to acquire, process, and visualize data of pits that serve as entrances to lava tubes, with a focus on lunar exploration [1]. The main instrument to perform this task is an hyperhemispheric camera, which is a single lense with the capability of capturing information in 360° degrees above the horizontal level (**Figure 1**). This extensive range of acquisition make DaedalusCAM ideal to survey closed environments like pits or collapses, which in lunar settings are usually related to lava tubes or void beneath impact melts [2, 3]. A mission concept with this technology would involve the descent of the DaedalusCAM through a pit and into the first meters of a lava tube, so the capabilities of the camera would be essential for navigation and collecting scientific information about the pit walls. In this work, we share initial results about two test campaigns done in analogue environments. We evaluated the capacity of DaedalusCAM to recognize geological features, by comparing its results to other techniques that are commonly applied in terrestrial settings.

Figure 1: Configuration DaedalusCAM [1].

Data and Methodology: To compare the results of DaedalusCAM with a ground truth, we will analyze three types of datasets: measurements of digital outcrop models reconstructed from a ground laser scanner, drone flights, and hyperspectral cameras (control models); measurements of digital models reconstructed from DaedalusCAM and an embedded LiDAR system; and measurements taken on the field by classical geological methods (scanlines and stratigraphic columns). At this point of the project, the analysis of the first datasets is complete, and the other two will be done in the following months.

The data of the control digital models was collected during two field campaigns in 2025, one to Lanzarote, in Spain, and other to Mount Etna, in Italy. From Lanzarote, we collected information from “Jameo de la Gente”, a collapse leading into La Corona tube; and from Etna, we collected information from the collapses of the Tre Livelli and Intraleo tubes, and from the Cisternazza volcanic collapse. We reconstructed 3D models for these locations using Cyclone and CloudCompare; hyperclouds using Blender and Python; and we performed geological measurements using the VRGS software.

The final acquisitions of DaedalusCAM will be done on April and May of 2026, digital models will be derived using a similar workflow, and the measurements will be also done in VRGS. Finally, the on-site measurements will be carried out simultaneously during the final acquisition of DaedalusCAM.

Results: The digital models for the locations were successfully reconstructed (**Figure 2**). The point clouds were processed in CloudCompare to make 3D mesh. To include hyperspectral information, we recreated the scene positions in Blender and then used the Hylite python Package to create hyperclouds [4].

Figure 2: On top 3D model of Tre Livelli in Etna, down the 3d Model of Jameo de la Gente in Lanzarote.

To perform the comparison of the datasets, we then developed a table with 23 features to measure in the three datasets that we defined (**Table 1**). These

features can be group in three categories: structural, morphological, and cavity. For the structural component we focused on fractures, striations, and grooves, which give information about how the lava tube formed and its internal dynamic. The second components is about identifying typical morphologies that form inside and near the entrance of tubes. And the final one is about the volume and size of the explored cavity.

Type	Structure	Measurements
Structural	Fractures	Amount of fractures in a scanline.
		Persistence, orientation, aperture.
	Striation	Orientation: azimuth and dip. Quantity.
	Grooves	Orientation: azimuth and dip. Quantity.
Morphological	Flow ledges	Lateral extension of the ledge from the wall.
		Vertical extension of the ledge.
	Stalactites and stalacmites	Quantity of structures identified.
		Length of the structures.
	Rolling-overs	Diameter of the coiled structure.
Curvature of the foil.		
Lining walls	Presence of absence of the structure.	
Cavity	Cavity/Outcrop	Measurements of the long and short diameters.
		Measurement of the area of the pit.
	Cave/Outcrop	Measurement of the volume of the pit or structure.

Table 1: Measurements done in the three datasets.

The measurement of the control digital models was done in VRGS. We retrieved the orientation, dip, persistence, and spacing of lava layers and fractures (**Figure 3**). We also measured the properties of the cavities, and then registered the presence of morphological structures when visible.

Figure 3: To the left the orientation of the lava layers, to the right the one of the fractures.

Discussion and conclusion: The measurements on the control models returned important lessons. The datasets obtained with the laser scanner and the drone have high spatial resolution, allowing the

measurement of more than three hundred layers and fractures. We do not expect the same level of accuracy from the DaedalusCAM derived models. Nevertheless, images obtained by this instruments in the Intraleo collapse can resolve middle-size fractures, as well as capturing color changes in the lava layers due to alteration; so meaningful information can still be retrieved by the system. Once the datasets are taken, a detailed comparison will be done by checking the trend and number of detections.

The analysis of Jameo de la Gente also gave light about the structural pattern of these environments. All terrestrial lava tubes are geologically recent, as a result, tectonic efforts are not the driven factors of fracturing, which is instead controlled by thermal cooling and by the geometry of the collapse [5]. This will not be the case for lunar lava tubes, which have been formed many hundred of million of years ago, and which will likely record the tectonic history of the basin that host them.

In conclusion, DaedalusCAM have versatile instruments that can explore hardly-accessible lunar locations; but determining the accuracy of the geological measurements derived form is necessary to propose an effective adquisition plan. So far, the system is able to resolve lineaments and color changes, but the upcoming analysis will validate its statistical accuracy.

References:

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